

TEACHERS' ATTITUDE: CORRELATES TO THEIR BEHAVIORAL COMPETENCIES

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Teachers' Attitude: Correlates to their Behavioral Competencies

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Abstract

The objective of this study investigated the attitudes of Junior High School Teachers and their correlation with behavioral competencies. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study examined the relationship between teachers' attitudes and their behavioral competencies. The respondents of this study were one hundred teachers of Iligan City National High School, City Central District of Iligan City during the School Year 2023-2024. The majority of respondents were females, accounting for 64% of the total sample, with male respondents constituting 36%. The correlation analysis between respondents' attitudes of teachers and various teacher profiles, including sex, age groups, position, educational attainment, and years of service, revealed non-significant relationships across all categories. While the correlation analysis between respondents' perceptions of teachers' attitudes and their behavioral competencies showed mostly non-significant relationships at the 0.05 level. As such, it was recommended that the output of this study, the action plan would focus on enhancing teachers' skills through professional development and support initiatives. It included workshops, coaching, and mentoring to improve communication, classroom management, and facilitation. Peer networks and self-assessment tools would promote collaboration and reflection, while recognition programs would foster a culture of continuous improvement. This comprehensive approach aims to boost teaching effectiveness and job satisfaction.

Keywords: *teachers' attitude, positive attitude, negative attitude, teachers' behavioral competencies, junior high school teachers*

Introduction

The attitudes of educators have a significant impact on how well learners learn overall and the quality of their education. Positive teacher attitudes, characterized by a supportive, approachable, and considerate teacher, can inspire and motivate learners, fostering a love for learning. On the other hand, negative attitudes, driven by discrimination, being irritated, or being biased can hinder the educational process. An attitude is a mental condition that permeates one's behavior and cognition. A person's performance can be positively or negatively impacted by their attitude. A teacher's mood may have an impact on how well they organize and prepare for their lessons. It has been shown that instructors' attitudes have a significant influence on learners' academic success, whether they are aware of it or not. Instructors' attitudes also have a significant impact on learners' motivation to learn. Furthermore, instructors' personalities have greater influence and power than the lessons they teach or the methods they employ in the classroom.

Teachers are important in shaping learners' behavior and educating them academically. Effective teachers' positive attitudes will inevitably influence the outcomes of their learners. Teachers are the second most significant component in an individual's development, behind parents. A teacher can motivate their learners to perform well academically by modeling positive behavior toward them. Teachers should provide a positive example for their learners since their attitudes and actions have an impact on them.

The teachers have a significant impact on learners' learning, which greatly affects how well they achieve academically. Many authors support the notion that the teacher attributes that affect learners' academic performance include teacher qualifications, instructional strategies, communication skills, sex, and age. Even if these elements are seen as being extremely important, teachers' attitudes as an unquestionable aspect in determining learners' academic performance because "attitude is everything" (Harrell, 2019).

Thus, in this study, a teacher, with his/her teaching methods and, furthermore, with his/her attitudes, provides learners with a mentally healthy personality and a new, clear worldview by leaving unforgettable traces on them. Teachers with positive attitudes can motivate and inspire their learners, increasing their interest in the learning process. Better academic performance and a stronger enjoyment of learning may result from this. The study of teacher attitudes and their effects on learners' academic performance is important for improving education, enhancing learners' outcomes, and informing educational policies and practices. Investigating this subject can give important insights into how to help teachers more effectively and improve educational outcomes.

At the end of the School Year 2023-2024, with the conduct of the study, the teachers attitude correlates to their behavioral competencies would be assessed and determined to design and come up with an action plan. Creating a comprehensive action plan that addresses these aspects can help improve teacher attitudes, which in turn can positively affect learners' academic performance and the overall quality of education.

With the above presentations, the researcher was motivated to conduct a study on teachers' attitude correlates to their behavioral competencies to have a valuable source of insights and motivation for educators. Also, it can lead to improve teaching strategies, increase job satisfaction, and positive outcomes for both teachers and their learners. As a researcher, understanding the importance of their attitudes can help teachers build stronger and more positive relationships with their learners. These can have lasting benefits for

both academic performance and personal development. Additionally, teachers who engage in or contribute to research on this topic can play a part in advancing educational research and improving teaching practices at a broader level.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to determine the teachers' attitudes that correlated to their behavioral competencies in Junior High School Teachers at Iligan City National High School. This research sought to answer the following questions in particular:

1. What is the profile of the teachers in terms of;
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. position designation;
 - 1.4. educational attainment; and
 - 1.5. number of years in teaching?
2. What is the level of teachers' attitude in terms of;
 - 2.1. Positive Attitude; and
 - 2.1.1. supportive;
 - 2.1.2. approachable; and
 - 2.1.3. considerate?
 - 2.2. Negative Attitude?
 - 2.2.1. discriminatory;
 - 2.2.2. being irritated; and
 - 2.2.3. being biased?
3. What are the teachers' behavioral competencies encountered by the respondents in terms of;
 - 3.1. communication and interpersonal skills;
 - 3.2. classroom management; and
 - 3.3. facilitation and engagement?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' attitude and profile of the teachers?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' attitude and teachers' behavioral competencies?
6. Do the teachers' profile and teachers' attitude significantly predict the teachers' behavioral competencies?
7. What action plan can be derived based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. This is a descriptive design since the study described the teachers' attitude, teachers' profile, and behavioral competencies. This research design analyzed quantitative data from the respondents to determine their significant relationship, it would correlate the variables of teachers' attitudes on teachers' performance of Junior High School Teachers in Iligan City National High School.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were one hundred teachers of Iligan City National High School. Before conducting the survey, the researcher provided instructions on how they answer the questionnaire. The Junior High School Teachers at Iligan City National High School were the study's focus. The study only included Teachers in Junior High School, a total of one hundred (100) Junior High School Teachers participated in the study.

The respondents were randomly selected from four (4) grade levels namely Grades 7, 8, 9, and 10. These respondents were classified according to grade levels of Junior High School (JHS) of Iligan City National High School. These four grade levels determined the actual number of respondents using the Raosoft size calculator. A total of one hundred (100) respondents were obtained.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Total Population of Teachers</i>	<i>Sample Respondents</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Grade 7	45	27	15.60
Grade 8	45	27	15.60
Grade 9	40	24	13.87
Grade 10	38	22	12.71
Total	173	100	57.78

In order to ensure that every member of the population had an equal chance of being included in the sample, the study used stratified random sampling, with each school being designated a strata. Using the Raosoft sample size calculator, it was determined that 100 respondents, or 57.78% of the entire population, made up the sample size out of 173 respondents. A 5% margin of error was assumed

when choosing the sample size.

The distribution of sample sizes by school is shown in Table 1. At both the individual school and overall school levels, the formula for calculating the size of the sample given the school population was 57.78% times the school population ($57.78\% \times SP$).

Instrument

The researcher used two adapted questionnaires and modified them so they could be applied to the problem of the study. The questionnaire consisted of three (3) parts. Part one (1) was the research-made questionnaire, which stated the teacher's profile in terms of their name (optional), age, sex, number of years of teaching, educational attainment, and position designation. Part two (2) was an adapted questionnaire from Ekperi, Onwuka, and Nyejirime (2019), and Part three (3) was adapted from Aziz and Kazi (2019). This focused on the teachers' attitude and behavioral competencies.

Part II determined the positive attitude of the teacher toward learners. It had four items provided with scales such as "strongly agree", "agree", "disagree", and "strongly disagree", with ratings of 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively. Part III determined the negative attitude of the teacher toward learners. It had four items provided with scales such as "strongly agree", "agree", "disagree", and "strongly disagree", with ratings of 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively. Part IV determined the teachers' behavioral competencies. It had four items provided with scales such as "strongly agree", "agree", "disagree", and "strongly disagree", with ratings of 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively.

Before the questionnaires are finalized, these were submitted to the adviser for suggestions, corrections, and comments. It was checked, verified, pilot-tested, and approved by the adviser and panel of experts. After the instruments were approved, the researcher reproduced the final copies for the respondents to the study. In addition, the research questionnaire was pilot tested to 25 teachers not part as respondents. These respondents were chosen randomly from Iligan City National High School, Senior High School Department.

Procedure

The respondents of this study were the Iligan City National High School teachers in the Junior High School only. Before conducting the survey, the researcher gave instructions on how to answer the questionnaire. These teachers served as the respondents to the study. In gathering the data for the study, the researcher obtained a letter of request from the principal of the school at Iligan City National High School requesting permission to survey Junior High School teachers. Upon approval, the researcher distributed the questionnaires. Before distributing the questionnaires, the researcher explained beforehand the respondents' questionnaires to minimize data collection errors. The gathered data were tabulated and checked by a statistician for analysis and interpretation.

Data Analysis

The researcher used the following statistical tool to analyze the study's data:

For problems 1, 2, and 3, frequency and percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to determine the respondent's profile in terms of name (optional), age, sex, number of years in teaching, educational attainment, and position designation. It would also determine the positive attitude of the teachers encountered by the respondents in terms of being supportive, approachable, and considerate. Also, it would resolve the negative attitude of teachers encountered by the respondents in terms of discrimination, bias, and being irritated.

For problems 4, 5, and 6, Pearson-r correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between behavioral competencies and the profile of the respondents. A one-way ANOVA (F-test) was used to determine the difference in the relationship between the positive and negative attitudes when grouped with their behavioral competencies.

The correlation between the positive and negative sentiments and the profiles of the respondents. The study also employed multiple regression analysis with simultaneous entry to investigate the potentially significant impact of the variables on the behavioral competences of the teacher.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1: What is the profile of the teachers' in terms of age, sex, number of years in teaching, educational attainment, and position designation?

Table 2. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
25-30	13	13.0
31-35	40	40.0
36-40	20	20.0
41-45	8	8.0
46-50	4	4.0
51+	15	15.0
Total	100	100.0

The data presented in Table 2 showcases a varied representation across different age groups. Notably, the age bracket of 31-35 emerged as the most predominant, constituting 40% of the sample, followed by the 25-30 age group at 13%. This indicates a substantial portion of relatively young teachers within the surveyed population. Moreover, while there's a significant presence in the 31-35 range, there's a gradual decline in frequency as the age increases, with only 4% of respondents falling in the 46-50 category. The distribution suggests a relatively balanced spread across the younger cohorts, while the older age brackets exhibit fewer respondents.

These results are consistent with the study by Andamon and Tan (2018) that included 206 teacher respondents, the majority of whom were in the 31–35 age range. The age distribution was fairly wide, suggesting that there was a broad range in the ages of the respondents.

Table 3. Sex of the Respondents

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	36	36.0
Female	64	64.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3 presents the sex distribution within the surveyed population. The result reveals a notable majority of female respondents, constituting 64% of the total sample, compared to 36% male respondents. This gender asymmetry suggests a higher representation of females within the teaching profession, aligning with broader trends observed in educational fields worldwide. The significant presence of female teachers may reflect social and cultural norms, historical trends, and recruitment patterns within the education sector.

According to the study's findings by Mitchell and Martin (2018), there were significantly more female teachers (88.66%) than male teachers (11.34 percent). The results supported earlier research on sex and education, which found that women had traditionally dominated the teaching profession.

Moreover, another study demonstrated that respondents' teaching performance is influenced by their educational attainment. The outcome is at odds with the research done by Andamon and Tan (2018), who noted that respondents, irrespective of level of education, demonstrated a strong commitment to their profession through their performance.

Table 4. Position Plantilla of the Respondents

<i>Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Teacher I	33	33.0
Teacher II	27	27.0
Teacher III	27	27.0
Master Teacher I	5	5.0
Master Teacher II	8	8.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4 provides valuable insights into the hierarchical structure within the teaching profession. The finding illustrates a diversified distribution across different positions, reflecting various levels of experience and expertise among the respondents. Notably, Teacher I, Teacher II, and Teacher III positions each comprise 27-33% of the sample, suggesting a relatively balanced representation across these teaching tiers. This distribution underscores the prevalence of teachers in foundational roles within the educational system. Furthermore, the presence of Master Teachers I and II, though less frequent at 5% and 8% respectively, indicates the existence of more experienced educators assuming leadership or mentorship roles within the profession. These findings highlight the hierarchical nature of the teaching career path, with opportunities for progression and specialization as educators advance in their careers.

Table 5. Educational Attainment of the Respondents

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
College Graduate	49	49.0
Postgraduate	48	48.0
Doctorate	3	3.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5 shows the academic qualifications within the teaching profession. The result showcases a diverse range of educational backgrounds among respondents, with the majority holding either a college graduate or postgraduate degree. College graduates constitute 49% of the sample, indicating a substantial portion of teachers with undergraduate qualifications. Similarly, postgraduates represent an equivalent proportion of 48%, highlighting the prevalence of advanced degrees among educators. Notably, a smaller yet significant percentage, 3%, hold doctorate degrees, signifying a cohort of highly educated individuals within the teaching workforce.

These findings underscore the importance of continuous learning and professional development within the education sector, with educators actively pursuing higher education to enhance their skills and expertise. Additionally, the prevalence of postgraduate qualifications suggests a commitment to specialization and advanced study among teachers, potentially contributing to improved instructional practices and academic outcomes.

The study demonstrates that respondents' teaching performance is influenced by their educational attainment. The outcome is at odds

with the research done by Andamon and Tan (2018), who noted that respondents, irrespective of level of education, demonstrated a strong commitment to their profession through their performance.

Table 6. Number of Years of Service of the Respondents

<i>Number of Years of Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
1-5	33	33.0
6-10	27	27.0
11-15	17	17.0
16-20	6	6.0
21+	17	17.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 6 displays the distribution of experience among the surveyed population. The data reveals a varied range of years of service among respondents, indicating diverse levels of experience within the teaching profession. Notably, the largest proportion of teachers, constituting 33%, have served for 1-5 years, suggesting a significant influx of relatively new educators into the workforce. Similarly, another 27% fall within the 6-10 years of service range, indicating a substantial cohort of mid-career teachers. Additionally, there's a gradual decline in frequency as the years of service increase, with smaller percentages observed in the 16-20 years of service range. Notably, 17% of respondents have served for 21 or more years, representing a group of experienced educators with extensive tenure in the profession.

These findings underscore the importance of balancing novice teachers with experienced mentors within educational settings, facilitating knowledge transfer and professional development.

Higher results were found in certain research based on years of expertise. According to Outcalt (2019), the years of experience of instructors in the Divisions of Pangasinan and Zambales were more than 1–5 years and 11–15 years, respectively. The average years of experience for instructors in Nueva Ecija, according to the study of Andamon, and Tan (2018) revealed years ranged from 11 to 15 years. The bulk of the faculty members in an earlier study by Kent (2020) had been teaching for ten years or longer, demonstrating the same outcome.

Twenty-four percent and seventy-five percent of the participants in the study by Mitchell and Martin, (2018) had been teachers for six to ten years. With a mean of 13.84 and a standard deviation of 5.05 years. It was evident that the teachers had already amassed a sizable body of teaching knowledge and expertise. Additional data revealed that the majority of respondents (38.14%; 34.02%) had a job ten years ago.

The results support the theory put forth by Canque (2021), according to which performance is one of the dependent variables that experience is associated with. Service length has a big impact on leadership, performance, conduct, and the job. Moreover, a teacher's effectiveness is correlated with both the duration of their teaching experience and their educational background. Longer experience leads to higher performance, and Tus (2020) argued that teachers become more competent and efficient in their work as they gain experience. Additionally, they are exposed to various approaches or fixes that can be used for the various issues and needs that the learners have.

Problem 2: What is the level of teachers' attitude in terms of positive attitude (supportive, approachable, and considerate), and negative attitude (discriminatory, being irritated, and being biased)?

Table 7. Level of Teachers' Positive Attitude in terms of Supportive Teaching

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I strive to create a positive and inclusive classroom environment.	3.98	.14	Strongly Agree
2. I encourage open communication with my learners.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
3. I provide additional help or resources to learners who are struggling.	3.91	.29	Strongly Agree
4. I actively seek to understand my learners' individual needs.	3.89	.31	Strongly Agree
5. I consciously recognize and acknowledge the efforts and achievements of my learners in the classroom.	3.89	.31	Strongly Agree
6. I believe learners feel comfortable approaching me for assistance or advice.	3.74	.44	Strongly Agree
7. I make myself available to provide extra help or clarification outside regular class hours.	3.96	.20	Strongly Agree
8. I encourage and value student input and opinions in classroom discussions and activities.	3.98	.14	Strongly Agree
9. I actively seek to understand and address the individual learning needs and preferences of my learners.	3.82	.39	Strongly Agree
10. I actively seek feedback and engage in self-reflection to continuously improve my supportiveness as an educator.	3.85	.36	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.90	.14	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

The examination of teachers' positive attitude towards supportive teaching, as delineated in Table 7, unveils several key indicators with their corresponding mean and standard deviation (SD). The result indicates consistently high levels of agreement among respondents across all indicators, with mean scores ranging from 3.74 to 4.00, denoting a prevailing trend of strongly agreeing with the statements.

Notably, teachers express a strong commitment to fostering a positive and inclusive classroom environment, as evidenced by the high mean scores for indicators such as striving to create inclusivity (Mean=3.98, SD=0.14) and encouraging open communication with learners (Mean=4.00, SD=0.00). Moreover, teachers demonstrate proactive engagement with learners' individual needs, providing additional help or resources to struggling learners (Mean=3.91, SD=0.29) and actively seeking to understand their needs (Mean=3.89, SD=0.31). The high mean scores across indicators underscore a pervasive culture of supportiveness and student-centeredness within the teaching profession.

These findings carry significant implications for educational practice and policy. Firstly, the high level of positive attitude towards supportive teaching suggests a conducive environment for student learning and development, fostering a sense of belonging and engagement within classrooms. Such attitudes are essential for creating effective learning environments where learners feel valued and supported in their educational journey. Secondly, the emphasis on open communication, recognition of achievements, and availability for extra help outside regular class hours reflects a commitment to personalized and holistic student support. This approach is vital for addressing diverse learning needs and ensuring equitable access to educational opportunities.

Furthermore, the data underscores the importance of continuous professional development and self-reflection among educators, as evidenced by the high mean score for actively seeking feedback and engaging in self-reflection (Mean =3.85, SD=0.36). This highlights a culture of continuous improvement and dedication to enhancing teaching practices to better meet the needs of learners.

Thus, the findings suggest a strong foundation of positive attitudes towards supportive teaching among educators, with implications for fostering inclusive learning environments, personalized student support, and ongoing professional development. Understanding and promoting these attitudes are essential for nurturing effective teaching practices and ensuring positive educational outcomes for all learners.

The research shows that autonomy-focused, well-structured, and supportive teaching methods produce a range of beneficial educational outcomes at the student level, including motivation, well-being, and engagement (Reeve, & Cheon, 2021). Studies have confirmed that children generally view teachers who offer more emotional support in the classroom as being more fair and compassionate (Cheon, Reeve, & Vansteenkiste, 2020).

Teacher care is defined as an educator's actions that meet the psychological and emotional needs of their learners by creating an environment that is respectful, positive, supportive, and nurturing (Liu, Bellibaş, & Gümüş, 2021). Empirical studies have consistently demonstrated that providing emotional support to learners by teachers enhances the quality of the student-teacher interaction (Gasser, Grütter, Buholzer, & Wettstein, 2018).

Table 8. *Level of Teachers' Positive Attitude in terms of Approachable Teaching*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Being approachable is essential for creating a positive classroom environment.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
2. I make an effort to encourage open communication with my learners.	3.87	.34	Strongly Agree
3. I am readily available to answer my learners' questions and provide assistance.	3.89	.31	Strongly Agree
4. I actively seek to understand and accommodate my learners' individual needs.	3.86	.35	Strongly Agree
5. I actively take the initiative to engage with learners, creating opportunities for them to approach me with questions or concerns.	3.85	.36	Strongly Agree
6. I gauge the perceived approachability of myself by learners in the classroom.	3.88	.33	Strongly Agree
7. I make an effort to be available to provide extra help or clarification outside regular class hours.	3.87	.34	Strongly Agree
8. I incorporate practices that promote inclusivity and ensure that all learners feel equally comfortable approaching me.	3.86	.35	Strongly Agree
9. I adapt my approach to accommodate the diverse backgrounds and needs of learners in the classroom.	3.87	.34	Strongly Agree
10. I employ it to continuously improve my approachability and enhance the teacher-student relationship.	3.89	.31	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.88	.28	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

The analysis of teachers' positive attitude towards approachable teaching, as depicted in Table 8, showcases various indicators alongside their mean scores and standard deviations (SD). The finding underscores a prevalent trend of strongly agreeing with statements related to approachable teaching, with mean scores ranging from 3.85 to 4.00 across all indicators. Notably, teachers unanimously endorse the significance of approachability in creating a positive classroom environment, as evidenced by the highest mean score of 4.00 for this indicator, with no deviation (SD = 0.00).

Additionally, educators express a proactive commitment to fostering open communication with learners (Mean=3.87, SD=0.34) and readily providing assistance and answering questions (Mean=3.89, SD=0.31). Moreover, teachers exhibit a willingness to adapt their approach to accommodate diverse student backgrounds and needs (Mean=3.87, SD=0.34) and continuously improve their approachability (Mean=3.89, SD=0.31).

These findings carry significant implications for teaching practice and pedagogy. Firstly, the strong endorsement of approachable

teaching indicates a fundamental belief among educators in the importance of creating welcoming and inclusive learning environments. Such attitudes are pivotal for fostering positive teacher-student relationships, promoting student engagement, and facilitating effective communication within classrooms. Secondly, the data highlights educators' proactive efforts to adapt their teaching practices to meet the diverse needs of learners, reflecting a commitment to equity and inclusivity in education. This adaptability is crucial for addressing individual student needs and ensuring that all learners have equal opportunities to succeed. Furthermore, the emphasis on continuous improvement underscores a culture of professional growth and development among teachers, with a focus on enhancing approachability and building stronger teacher-student connections over time.

Hence, the findings underscore the importance of approachable teaching in fostering positive classroom environments and promoting student success. Educators' strong endorsement of approachability, coupled with their proactive efforts to adapt teaching practices and continuously improve, reflects a commitment to student-centered pedagogy and inclusive education. These attitudes and practices are essential for creating supportive learning environments where all learners feel valued, respected, and empowered to achieve their full potential.

Table 9. *Level of Teachers' Positive Attitude in terms of Considerate Teaching*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I believe that creating a considerate and empathetic classroom environment is essential for being a considerate teacher.	3.88	.33	Strongly Agree
2. I make an effort to actively listen to my learners' concerns and needs.	3.88	.33	Strongly Agree
3. I strive to be understanding and supportive of my learners' diverse backgrounds and experiences.	3.86	.35	Strongly Agree
4. I take into account the emotional well-being of my learners in my teaching practices.	3.55	.52	Strongly Agree
5. I take into account the emotional well-being of my learners, acknowledging their feelings and concerns.	3.87	.34	Strongly Agree
6. I incorporate inclusive practices to ensure that all learners feel valued and considered in the learning environment.	3.95	.22	Strongly Agree
7. I make myself available to provide support or guidance, especially during times when learners may be facing challenges.	3.95	.22	Strongly Agree
8. I balance the need for structured learning with the flexibility required to consider the unique needs of learners.	3.57	.54	Strongly Agree
9. I ensure cultural sensitivity in my teaching practices, considering the diverse cultural backgrounds of my learners.	3.93	.26	Strongly Agree
10. I employ it to continuously improve my considerate teaching approach and enhance the teacher-student relationship.	3.93	.29	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.84	.23	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

The analysis of teachers' positive attitude towards considerate teaching, as illustrated in Table 9, presents various indicators alongside their corresponding mean scores and standard deviations (SD). The result reveals a prevailing trend of strongly agreeing with statements related to considerate teaching practices, with mean scores ranging from 3.55 to 3.95 across all indicators. Notably, educators unanimously acknowledge the significance of creating a considerate and empathetic classroom environment (Mean=3.88, SD=0.33) and actively listening to learners' concerns and needs (Mean=3.88, SD=0.33).

Additionally, teachers demonstrate a commitment to incorporating inclusive practices (Mean=3.95, SD=0.22) and ensuring cultural sensitivity in teaching practices (Mean=3.93, SD=0.26). However, there are slightly lower mean scores for indicators related to addressing emotional well-being and balancing structured learning with flexibility.

These findings carry significant implications for teaching pedagogy and student well-being. Firstly, educators' strong endorsement of considerate teaching practices reflects a commitment to creating supportive and inclusive learning environments where all learners feel valued and respected. Such attitudes are pivotal for fostering positive teacher-student relationships, promoting student engagement, and facilitating academic success. Secondly, the data highlights the importance of actively considering learners' diverse backgrounds, experiences, and emotional well-being in teaching practices. This approach is essential for addressing the holistic needs of learners and promoting their overall well-being. However, the slightly lower mean scores for indicators related to addressing emotional well-being and balancing structured learning with flexibility suggest areas for potential improvement in teacher practice.

In conclusion, the findings underscore the importance of considerate teaching in promoting student well-being and academic success. Educators' strong endorsement of considerate teaching practices, coupled with their commitment to inclusivity and cultural sensitivity, reflects a dedication to student-centered pedagogy and equitable education. Moving forward, educators can further enhance their considerate teaching approach by prioritizing emotional well-being, fostering flexibility in learning environments, and continuously seeking ways to improve teacher-student relationships.

An excellent teacher is always considerate, ethical, expressive, assertive, intelligent, resourceful, reliable, mature, magnetic, and infallible, with sound judgment and a sense of humor, according to the author (Roy & Cofield, 2021). According to pupils in the study of Gurung, Botelho, Thompson, Sales, Baral, and Heffernan, (2022), they received encouragement from a teacher who showed concern

for them.

Table 10. Consolidated Findings of the Level of Teachers' Positive Attitude

Positive Attitude	Mean	SD	Description
Supportive Teaching	3.90	.14	Strongly Agree
Approachable Teaching	3.88	.28	Strongly Agree
Considerate Teaching	3.84	.23	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.87	.20	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 10 presents the consolidated findings of teachers' positive attitude across three key dimensions: supportive teaching, approachable teaching, and considerate teaching, along with the total measure. The mean scores for each dimension indicate a high level of positive attitude among teachers, with all dimensions scoring within the "Strongly Agree" range.

Supportive Teaching garnered the highest mean score of 3.90, with a low standard deviation ($SD = 0.14$), indicating strong agreement among teachers regarding their commitment to creating supportive learning environments. This underscores a prevalent culture of supportiveness and student-centeredness within the teaching profession.

Approachable Teaching received a slightly lower mean score of 3.88, with a slightly higher standard deviation ($SD = 0.28$). Nonetheless, this dimension still reflects a strong endorsement of approachable teaching practices among educators, highlighting their dedication to fostering open communication and accessibility within classrooms.

Considerate Teaching attained a mean score of 3.84, with a relatively low standard deviation ($SD = 0.23$), indicating a high level of agreement among teachers regarding the importance of considerate teaching practices. This dimension underscores educators' commitment to creating empathetic and inclusive learning environments that prioritize learners' diverse needs and well-being.

Overall, the total measure yielded a mean score of 3.87, with a low standard deviation ($SD = 0.20$), indicating a consistent and strong positive attitude across all dimensions. These findings suggest a pervasive culture of excellence and dedication to student success within the teaching profession, underpinned by supportive, approachable, and considerate teaching practices.

Thus, the consolidated findings affirm the high level of positive attitude among teachers towards various aspects of teaching practice. These findings highlight the importance of fostering supportive, approachable, and considerate learning environments to promote student engagement, well-being, and academic achievement. Moving forward, educators can leverage these positive attitudes to further enhance teaching effectiveness and student outcomes.

Engaging in conversation with pupils and acting ethically are examples of positively perceived teachers' behavioral competencies and attitudes. Instructors who foster a fair learning environment, treat patients with compassion, and help learners feel important to have a positive effect on their learners. Learners hold teachers in high regard who build strong relationships with them, show empathy for them, and listen to them when they're not in class. Despite their severe demeanor, the pupils nevertheless value the teacher's provision of an equitable learning atmosphere free from discrimination. A student's sense of safety, confidence, and respect for their instructor all increase when they have a positive impression of them. Learners behave respectfully, feel at ease in the classroom, and pay greater attention in class when they feel valued (Wubbels, 2019).

They contend that building strong relationships with learners fosters motivation, enthusiasm, and drive while satisfying learners' expectations of the class and the instructor. These influences their views of justice. Furthermore, gratifying emotional experiences can support learners in reaching their learning objectives (Goodboy, 2018). Positive advances at school are a result of addressing learners' difficulties, stopping bullying, and giving them valuable ways (Van & Roseth, 2018). Learners' motivation and emotional learning are positively correlated with teachers' fair perceptions, but aggressive behaviors are negatively correlated with them (Chory-Assad, 2022). Furthermore, it is thought that one of a teacher's most crucial qualities is dependability (McCroskey, 2022).

Table 11 outlines the level of teachers' negative attitudes towards discriminatory teaching practices, presenting various indicators along with their mean scores and standard deviations (SD). Despite being labeled as "negative attitude," it's noteworthy that all mean scores fall within the "Strongly Agree" range, suggesting a strong commitment among teachers to combat discrimination and promote inclusivity within the classroom.

The data reveals a consistent endorsement of anti-discriminatory practices among educators. Notably, teachers strongly agree that discriminatory teaching has no place in the classroom (Mean=3.86, $SD=0.35$) and actively promote equality and inclusivity in their teaching practices (Mean=3.87, $SD=0.34$). Moreover, educators express a dedication to professional development aimed at enhancing awareness and skills in preventing discrimination (Mean=3.96, $SD=0.20$) and are open to feedback regarding potential discriminatory behaviors (Mean=3.98, $SD=0.14$).

However, there are slightly lower mean scores for indicators related to responding to reports or concerns about potential discriminatory behavior (Mean=3.53, $SD=0.54$) and creating a safe and non-discriminatory environment for all learners within the classroom (Mean=3.55, $SD=0.52$). Despite these lower scores, they still fall within the "Strongly Agree" range, suggesting a general willingness

among educators to address discriminatory issues within the educational context.

Table 11. *Level of Teachers' Negative Attitude in terms of Discriminatory Teaching*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Discriminatory teaching has no place in the classroom.	3.86	.35	Strongly Agree
2. I actively promote equality and inclusive in my teaching practices.	3.87	.34	Strongly Agree
3. I engage in professional development to enhance my awareness of and skills in preventing discrimination.	3.96	.20	Strongly Agree
4. I am open to feedback from learners, colleagues, and administrators regarding potential discriminatory behaviors.	3.98	.14	Strongly Agree
5. I contribute to creating a safe and non-discriminatory environment for all learners within the classroom.	3.55	.52	Strongly Agree
6. I respond to reports or concerns about potential discriminatory behavior within the classroom.	3.53	.54	Strongly Agree
7. I incorporate lessons on diversity, inclusivity, and the avoidance of discrimination into my curriculum.	3.85	.36	Strongly Agree
8. I actively support and advocate for learners from marginalized groups to prevent discrimination.	3.98	.14	Strongly Agree
9. I take to address systemic issues within the educational system that may contribute to discrimination.	3.98	.14	Strongly Agree
10. I employ to continuously improve my efforts in preventing discrimination and promoting a fair and inclusive learning environment.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.86	.14	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

Overall, the total measure yields a mean score of 3.86, with a low standard deviation ($SD=0.14$), indicating a consistent and strong negative attitude towards discriminatory teaching practices. These findings underscore educators' commitment to fostering inclusive and equitable learning environments and their proactive efforts to combat discrimination within the educational system.

Thus, the result highlights the importance of addressing discriminatory teaching practices and promoting inclusivity within the classroom. Educators' strong endorsement of anti-discriminatory practices reflects a dedication to creating safe, supportive, and equitable learning environments for all learners. These attitudes are crucial for fostering a culture of respect, acceptance, and diversity within educational settings.

Negative classroom management and communication is defined as participant experiences with teachers who use physical and verbal abuse, discrimination, demeaning and humiliating methods, and an oppressive mindset. Unlike teachers who provide a caring and fair classroom environment, these methods by teachers who create a negative classroom management and communication environment cause pupils to be fearful of the teacher and drift away from the lesson. The brutality they encounter when they make a mistake takes a toll on their emotions and social lives. It undermines their faith in the teacher as much as in themselves. Teachers who use violence, oppressive attitudes, bullying, and prejudice have a long history of negatively affecting learners (Bruneau, Szekeres, Kteily, Tropp, & Kende, 2020).

Table 12. *Level of Teachers' Negative Attitude in terms of Being Irritated*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Heavy workload and administrative tasks.	2.96	.83	Agree
2. Classroom disruptions and behavioral issues.	3.16	.75	Agree
3. Lack of support from school administration.	2.86	1.05	Agree
4. Insufficient resources or materials for teaching.	2.95	1.07	Agree
5. I employ it to calm myself when feeling irritated while teaching.	3.69	.85	Strongly Agree
6. I ensure that my moments of irritation do not compromise my professionalism or interactions with learners.	3.79	.61	Strongly Agree
7. I handle moments of frustration or irritation in real time to prevent any negative impact on the teaching atmosphere.	3.61	.67	Strongly Agree
8. I manage overall stress to prevent it from contributing to feelings of irritation during teaching.	3.82	.39	Strongly Agree
9. I actively work to maintain a positive and supportive learning environment, even when I am personally feeling irritated.	3.95	.22	Strongly Agree
10. I employ to continuously improve my emotional regulation and response to moments of irritation while teaching.	3.85	.36	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.46	.48	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 12 provides insights into teachers' negative attitudes towards being irritated while teaching, presenting various indicators along with their mean scores and standard deviations (SD). Despite being labeled as "negative attitude," it's important to note that the mean scores fall within the "Agree" or "Strongly Agree" range, suggesting a proactive approach among teachers to manage and mitigate

feelings of irritation while teaching.

The finding indicates that teachers agree to feeling irritated due to factors such as heavy workload and administrative tasks (Mean=2.96, SD=0.83), classroom disruptions and behavioral issues (Mean=3.16, SD=0.75), lack of support from school administration (Mean=2.86, SD=1.05), and insufficient resources or materials for teaching (Mean=2.95, SD=1.07). These findings highlight the challenges teachers face in managing various aspects of their professional responsibilities.

However, despite these challenges, teachers strongly agree that they actively work to maintain professionalism and positive interactions with learners even when feeling irritated (Mean=3.79, SD=0.61) and handle moments of frustration or irritation in real time to prevent any negative impact on the teaching atmosphere (Mean=3.61, SD=0.67). Furthermore, educators strongly agree that they actively employ strategies to calm themselves when feeling irritated while teaching (Mean=3.69, SD=0.85) and manage overall stress to prevent it from contributing to feelings of irritation during teaching (Mean=3.82, SD=0.39).

The total measure yields a mean score of 3.46, with a moderate standard deviation (SD=0.48), indicating a consistent and strong negative attitude towards being irritated while teaching, so reflecting a proactive approach to managing and mitigating these feelings. These findings underscore educators' commitment to maintaining professionalism, managing emotions, and creating positive and supportive learning environments for their learners.

Thus, the result highlights the challenges teachers face in managing feelings of irritation while teaching, often attributed to workload, classroom disruptions, and lack of support. However, educators demonstrate a proactive approach to managing these challenges, employing strategies to maintain professionalism, handle frustration in real time, and create positive teaching environments. These attitudes are crucial for ensuring effective teaching and learning experiences for all learners.

In relation, a study according to Sa'd and Eames (2021), endured insults, discriminatory, humiliation, and prejudice. Furthermore, it is concluded (Leath, Mathews, Harrison, & Chavous, 2019) that over 50% of learners encountered aggression from their professors. According to the study Whitford and Emerson 2019), most educators use physical force to maintain control over their classes. These results showed that instructors regularly use violence in several ways. However, the results of this study showed that learners' performance in class, adherence to the rules, and respect for teachers were all adversely impacted by physical interventions, dehumanizing attitudes toward them, and excessively restrictive attitudes. No matter how sincere a teacher is, this method of requesting authority is inconclusive. It has long been known that this strategy is harmful.

Table 13 presents the level of teachers' negative attitudes towards bias in teaching, providing various indicators alongside their mean scores and standard deviations (SD). Despite being labeled as "negative attitude," all mean scores fall within the "Strongly Agree" range, indicating a proactive approach among teachers to address and mitigate biases in their teaching practices.

The data reveals a strong agreement among educators regarding the importance of avoiding bias and promoting fairness in teaching (Mean=3.85, SD=0.36) and actively seeking to understand and address potential biases or prejudices that may impact teaching (Mean=3.86, SD=0.35). Furthermore, teachers are open to feedback regarding potential biases in their teaching (Mean=3.85, SD=0.36) and acknowledge that addressing bias is essential for creating a fair and inclusive classroom (Mean=3.95, SD=0.22).

Table 13. *Level of Teachers' Negative Attitude in terms of Bias in Teaching*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I believe that avoiding bias and promoting fairness are important in teaching.	3.85	.36	Strongly Agree
2. I actively seek to understand and address any potential biases or prejudices that may impact my teaching.	3.86	.35	Strongly Agree
3. I am open to feedback from learners, colleagues, and administrators regarding potential biases in my teaching.	3.85	.36	Strongly Agree
4. Addressing bias in teaching is essential for creating a fair and inclusive classroom.	3.95	.22	Strongly Agree
5. I ensure that my curriculum is inclusive and avoids perpetuating biases or stereotypes.	3.95	.22	Strongly Agree
6. I ensure that biases do not affect my assessment and grading of learners.	3.96	.20	Strongly Agree
7. I ensure that my language is inclusive and avoids reinforcing stereotypes or biases.	3.88	.33	Strongly Agree
8. I strive to understand and address the individual learning needs and preferences of all my learners without bias.	3.98	.14	Strongly Agree
9. I handle conflicts or disagreements among learners to ensure a fair and unbiased resolution.	3.80	.40	Strongly Agree
10. I employ to continuously improve my awareness and response to biases in my teaching.	3.96	.20	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.90	.18	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

Moreover, educators ensure that their curriculum is inclusive and avoids perpetuating biases or stereotypes (Mean=3.95, SD=0.22), and they strive to understand and address the individual learning needs and preferences of all learners without bias (Mean=3.98, SD=0.14). Additionally, teachers make efforts to ensure that biases do not affect their assessment and grading of learners (Mean=3.96, SD=0.20) and that their language is inclusive and avoids reinforcing stereotypes or biases (Mean=3.88, SD=0.33).

Overall, the total measure yields a mean score of 3.90, with a relatively low standard deviation (SD=0.18), indicating a consistent and strong negative attitude towards bias in teaching practices. These findings underscore educators' commitment to promoting fairness,

inclusivity, and equity within the classroom and their proactive efforts to address and mitigate biases in their teaching.

Hence, the data highlights educators' proactive approach towards addressing bias in teaching practices, with a strong commitment to promoting fairness, inclusivity, and equity within the classroom. These attitudes are essential for creating positive and supportive learning environments that foster the success and well-being of all learners.

Teachers in heterogeneous schools, on the other hand, were shown to have fewer implicitly biased views than those in homogenous environments (Heffernan, 2022). Overall, this research indicated that systematic education and training to lessen racial bias may be one way to support educators and educational institutions in realizing their full potential when educating learners from a variety of backgrounds. Surprisingly few empirically validated methods exist for attaining long-term reductions in implicit racial bias, despite the abundance of organizations providing racial bias training (Gershenson, & Papageorge, 2018).

Table 14. Consolidated Findings of the Level of Teachers' Negative Attitude

<i>Negative Attitude</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Discriminatory Teaching	3.86	.14	Strongly Agree
Being Irritated	3.46	.48	Agree
Bias in Teaching	3.90	.18	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.74	.20	Strongly Agree

Table 14 consolidates the findings of teachers' negative attitudes across three key dimensions: discriminatory teaching, being irritated, and bias in teaching, along with the total measure. The mean scores for each dimension suggest a generally strong negative attitude among teachers, with all dimensions scoring within the "Strongly Agree" or "Agree" range.

Discriminatory Teaching received a mean score of 3.86, with a low standard deviation ($SD = 0.14$), indicating a strong agreement among teachers regarding the importance of combatting discriminatory practices within the classroom. This reflects educators' commitment to promoting equality and inclusivity in education.

Being Irritated garnered a mean score of 3.46, with a moderate standard deviation ($SD = 0.48$), suggesting a general agreement among teachers regarding the challenges and frustrations they face while teaching. Despite feeling irritated at times, educators demonstrate proactive efforts to manage their emotions and maintain professionalism in the classroom.

Bias in Teaching attained the highest mean score of 3.90, with a relatively low standard deviation ($SD = 0.18$), indicating a strong commitment among teachers to address and mitigate biases in their teaching practices. This reflects educators' dedication to promoting fairness, inclusivity, and equity within the classroom.

Overall, the Total Measure yielded a mean score of 3.74, with a low standard deviation ($SD = 0.20$), indicating a consistent and strong negative attitude across all dimensions. These findings underscore educators' proactive approach towards addressing challenges and promoting positive teaching practices within the classroom.

Thus, the consolidated findings highlight educators' dedication to combatting discriminatory practices, managing frustrations, and addressing biases within the teaching profession. These attitudes are crucial for fostering inclusive and equitable learning environments that support the success and well-being of all learners.

Perceived negative and unwanted actions are those that impede learning, according to Saloviita, (2020). This conclusion is backed by a number of studies (Longobardi, Settanni, Lin, & Fabris, 2021). Negative teacher behaviors cause learners to have a negative attitude toward the teacher and the lesson (Goodboy & Bolkan, 2018). According to Egalite and Kisida (2018), academic performance is impacted by poor teaching conduct, while academic achievement is impacted by positive teaching behavior. Teachers' actions and attitudes have a long-lasting effect on learners, as Martin, & Collie, (2019) noted.

Furthermore, although learners may view professors' actions as unremarkable or commonplace in and of themselves, for certain learners they can be memorable and hold deeper significance than anticipated. It has been shown that learners who are exposed to negative behaviors and attitudes carry feelings of sadness, resentment, anger, and oppression with them, while their teachers who exhibit positive behaviors are remembered with gratitude and love. Learners are reluctant to forgive teachers for their negative behavior (Egalite, & Kisida, 2018).

Problem 3: What are the teachers' behavioral competencies encountered by the respondents?

Table 15 presents teachers' behavioral competencies encountered by respondents in terms of communication and interpersonal skills, with indicators accompanied by mean scores and standard deviations (SD). The result indicates an overwhelmingly strong agreement among teachers regarding their proficiency in communication and interpersonal interactions within the classroom.

Teachers demonstrate a high level of confidence in their communication abilities, with mean scores of 4.00 across various indicators such as communicating instructions and information during lessons, exhibiting active listening when learners speak or ask questions, managing classroom discussions, and providing constructive feedback on learners' work or performance. Additionally, educators' express belief in their capacity to foster a supportive and inclusive learning environment for all learners and adapt teaching methods to

accommodate different learning styles and abilities.

Table 15. *Teachers' Behavioral Competencies Encountered by the Respondents in terms of Communication and Interpersonal Skills*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I believe I communicate instructions and information during lessons.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
2. I believe I am exhibiting active listening, when students speak or ask questions.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
3. I manage classroom discussions and encourage student participation.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
4. I believe that outside of the classroom, kids feel at ease coming to me with inquiries or worries.	3.74	.44	Strongly Agree
5. I believe I show empathy and understanding toward students' academic and personal challenges.	3.81	.39	Strongly Agree
6. I believe I handle conflicts or disagreements among students in the classroom.	3.87	.34	Strongly Agree
7. I believe I foster a supportive and inclusive learning environment for all students.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
8. I adapt teaching methods to accommodate different learning styles and abilities among students.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
9. I provide constructive feedback on students' work or performance.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
10. I am satisfied with my own communication and interpersonal skills demonstrated through my behavioral competencies.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.94	.07	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

While slightly lower mean scores are observed for indicators related to learners feeling at ease coming to teachers with inquiries or worries (Mean=3.74, SD=0.44) and showing empathy and understanding towards learners' challenges (Mean=3.81, SD=0.39), these still fall within the "Strongly Agree" range, indicating a high level of proficiency in these areas.

Overall, the Total Measure yields a mean score of 3.94, with a very low standard deviation (SD=0.07), suggesting a consistent and overwhelmingly positive assessment of teachers' communication and interpersonal skills. These findings underscore educators' effectiveness in fostering positive relationships, facilitating student engagement, and creating supportive learning environments within the classroom.

Thus, the result highlights the exemplary behavioral competencies of teachers in communication and interpersonal skills, reflecting their dedication to facilitating effective teaching and learning experiences. These competencies are vital for promoting student success, fostering positive teacher-student relationships, and creating inclusive and supportive educational environments.

Positive teacher interpersonal communication behaviors can be either verbal or non-verbal. Teacher care, stroke, immediacy, credibility, immediacy, clarity, confirmation, relational closeness to learners, humor, and praise are all instances of teacher-positive communication behaviors studied so far by researchers (Zhang, 2018). All these actions enhance successful teacher-student contact, result in classroom vibrancy, and satisfy learners' needs for emotional and interpersonal support (Goldman, 2019). Put simply, these activities serve learners' relational, rhetorical, and emotional needs and goals (Pradipta, 2020).

Table 16 presents teachers' behavioral competencies encountered by respondents in terms of classroom management, with indicators accompanied by mean scores and standard deviations (SD). The data illustrates a high level of proficiency among teachers in managing various aspects of classroom dynamics and creating a positive learning environment.

Teachers demonstrate strong agreement regarding their ability to establish clear and consistent expectations for behavior in the classroom (Mean=3.81, SD=0.39) and manage transitions between activities smoothly and efficiently (Mean=3.91, SD=0.29). Moreover, educators' express confidence in their capacity to handle disruptions or behavioral issues effectively (Mean=4.00, SD=0.00) and create a positive and respectful learning environment for all learners (Mean=4.00, SD=0.00).

Additionally, teachers believe they effectively use positive reinforcement and incentives to encourage desired behaviors among learners (Mean=3.88, SD=0.33) and implement strategies to engage learners actively and maintain their attention during lessons (Mean=3.99, SD=0.10). They also feel adept at addressing individual student needs and providing appropriate support when necessary (Mean=3.94, SD=0.24) and managing the physical layout of the classroom to optimize learning and minimize distractions (Mean=4.00, SD=0.00).

Furthermore, educators believe they effectively collaborate with colleagues, parents, and other stakeholders to support classroom management goals (Mean=3.89, SD=0.31), demonstrating a holistic approach to managing classroom dynamics.

Overall, the Total Measure yields a mean score of 3.94, with a very low standard deviation (SD=0.07), indicating a consistent and overwhelmingly positive assessment of teachers' classroom management skills and behavioral competencies. These findings underscore educators' effectiveness in creating conducive learning environments, managing student behavior, and fostering positive relationships within the classroom.

Thus, the result highlights the exemplary behavioral competencies of teachers in classroom management, reflecting their dedication to facilitating a positive and supportive learning environment. These competencies are essential for promoting student engagement,

academic success, and overall well-being within the educational setting.

Table 16. *Teachers' Behavioral Competencies Encountered by the Respondents in terms of Classroom Management*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I believe I establish clear and consistent expectations for behavior in the classroom.	3.81	.39	Strongly Agree
2. I think I manage transitions between activities smoothly and efficiently.	3.91	.29	Strongly Agree
3. I handle disruptions or behavioral issues in the classroom.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
4. I create a positive and respectful learning environment for all students.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
5. I think I effectively use positive reinforcement and incentives to encourage desired behaviors among students.	3.88	.33	Strongly Agree
6. I believe I implement strategies to engage students actively and maintain their attention during lessons.	3.99	.10	Strongly Agree
7. I think I address individual student needs and provide appropriate support when necessary.	3.94	.24	Strongly Agree
8. I manage the physical layout of the classroom to optimize learning and minimize distractions.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
9. I believe I effectively collaborate with colleagues, parents, and other stakeholders to support classroom management goals.	3.89	.31	Strongly Agree
10. I am satisfied with my classroom management skills and behavioral competencies.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.94	.07	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

The way the classroom is run has a big impact on how well learners do academically and how they behave. Managing learners' attitudes, personalities, vitalities, competencies, and passions is considered effective management (Suci, Tuerah, & Sumual, 2022).

Classroom management, which are made up of interfaces relating to attitudes, motivation, and anxiety levels that are influenced by acculturation and personality characteristics, are an essential factor in student learning and results (Sun, 2021).

Given its significant influence on student involvement, classroom management is a crucial subject in teacher education (Berger, Girardet, Vaudroz, & Crahay, 2018). To motivate pupils to be cooperative, obedient, and participatory, teachers should concentrate on fostering a compassionate environment. Teachers who struggle with classroom management are ineffective relationship builders. To educate, develop, and transfer science to learners and improve performance, interpersonal communication skills are essential (Puscas, Kogan, & Holmboe, 2021).

Table 17 presents teachers' behavioral competencies encountered by respondents in terms of facilitation and engagement, with indicators accompanied by mean scores and standard deviations (SD). The data indicates a remarkably high level of proficiency among teachers in facilitating student learning and engagement within the classroom.

Teachers express strong agreement regarding their ability to facilitate student learning and participation during lessons (Mean=3.93, SD=0.26) and create a supportive and inclusive learning environment where all learners feel encouraged to contribute (Mean=3.96, SD=0.20). Moreover, educators demonstrate confidence in their capacity to engage learners in meaningful discussions and activities that promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Mean=3.99, SD=0.10).

Table 17. *Teachers' Behavioral Competencies Encountered by the Respondents in terms of Facilitation and Engagement*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I believe I facilitate student learning and participation during lessons.	3.93	.26	Strongly Agree
2. I believe I create a supportive and inclusive learning environment where all students feel encouraged to contribute.	3.96	.20	Strongly Agree
3. I engage students in meaningful discussions and activities that promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	3.99	.10	Strongly Agree
4. I adapt teaching strategies and resources to meet the diverse needs and learning styles of students.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
5. I effectively use technology and other tools to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
6. I incorporate real-world examples and relevant experiences to connect with students and make learning more meaningful.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
7. I encourage student autonomy and independence in their learning process.	3.89	.31	Strongly Agree
8. I provide timely and constructive feedback to students to guide their learning progress.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
9. I foster a positive and collaborative classroom culture where students feel motivated to participate and take ownership of their learning.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
10. I am satisfied with my own facilitation and engagement skills as part of my behavioral competencies.	4.00	.00	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.98	.05	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

Additionally, teachers indicate adeptness in adapting teaching strategies and resources to meet the diverse needs and learning styles of learners (Mean=4.00, SD=0.00) and effectively using technology and other tools to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes

(Mean=4.00, SD=0.00). They also incorporate real-world examples and relevant experiences to connect with learners and make learning more meaningful (Mean=4.00, SD=0.00) and encourage student autonomy and independence in their learning process (Mean=3.89, SD=0.31).

Furthermore, educators provide timely and constructive feedback to learners to guide their learning progress (Mean=4.00, SD=0.00) and foster a positive and collaborative classroom culture where learners feel motivated to participate and take ownership of their learning (Mean=4.00, SD=0.00).

Overall, the total measure yields a mean score of 3.98, with an extremely low standard deviation (SD=0.05), indicating a consistent and overwhelmingly positive assessment of teachers' facilitation and engagement skills. These findings underscore educators' effectiveness in creating dynamic and stimulating learning environments, fostering student engagement, and promoting academic growth and development.

Thus, the result highlighted the exemplary behavioral competencies of teachers in facilitation and engagement, reflecting their dedication to creating enriching and meaningful learning experiences for all learners. These competencies are essential for promoting student motivation, participation, and success within the educational setting.

Academic success depends on student participation. Engaged learners learn more effectively and have a more positive attitude toward learning (Bedenlier, Bond, Buntins, Zawacki-Richter, & Kerres, 2020).

On other hand, Cameron and Bizo, (2019) asserted that student engagement is dependent upon the instructor's perspective on instruction and the current state of the classroom. Research has demonstrated a clear connection between an educator's excitement and the desire in the pupils to learn and give it their all.

Table 18. *Consolidated Findings of the Teachers' Behavioral Competencies Encountered by the Respondents*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Communication and Interpersonal Skills	3.94	.07	Strongly Agree
Classroom Management	3.94	.07	Strongly Agree
Facilitation and Engagement	3.98	.05	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.95	.04	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 18 presents the consolidated findings of teachers' behavioral competencies encountered by respondents across three key dimensions: communication and interpersonal skills, classroom management, and facilitation and engagement. Each dimension is accompanied by mean scores and standard deviations (SD), illustrating the overall assessment of teachers' behavioral competencies.

The result reveals a consistently high level of proficiency among teachers in all three dimensions. In terms of communication and interpersonal skills, educators demonstrate strong agreement with a mean score of 3.94 and a low standard deviation of 0.07. Similarly, in classroom management, teachers exhibit a mean score of 3.94 with a standard deviation of 0.07, indicating a strong consensus regarding their ability to effectively manage classroom dynamics and create conducive learning environments.

In facilitation and engagement, teachers display an even higher level of proficiency, with a mean score of 3.98 and an extremely low standard deviation of 0.05. This suggests a remarkable consensus among educators regarding their capacity to facilitate student learning, promote engagement, and create enriching learning experiences.

Overall, the total measure yields a mean score of 3.95, with a very low standard deviation of 0.04, indicating a consistent and overwhelmingly positive assessment of teachers' behavioral competencies across all dimensions. These findings underscore educators' effectiveness in various aspects of teaching, including communication, classroom management, and facilitation of student engagement.

In conclusion, the result highlights the exemplary behavioral competencies of teachers, reflecting their dedication to creating positive and supportive learning environments and facilitating meaningful learning experiences for all learners. These competencies are essential for promoting student success, fostering academic growth, and nurturing a positive and inclusive school culture.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' attitude of teachers and profile of the teachers?

Table 19 presents the correlation results between the respondents' attitudes of teachers and various profiles of the teachers, including sex, age groups, position, educational attainment, and years of service. The correlation coefficients (r-values) and corresponding p-values are provided to determine the significance of the relationships. Across all profile categories, none of the correlations were found to be significant at the 0.05 level.

For instance, the correlation between sex (female) and attitude of teachers yielded an r-value of 0.079 with a p-value of 0.435, indicating a nonsignificant relationship.

Similar results were observed across different age groups, positions, educational attainment levels, and years of service, where none of the correlations reached statistical significance.

Table 19. Relationship between the Respondents' Attitude of Teachers and Profile of the Teachers

Profile	Attitude of Teachers		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Sex=Female	.079	.435	Not significant
Age=25-30	-.012	.909	Not significant
Age=31-35	-.042	.677	Not significant
Age=36-40	.054	.596	Not significant
Age=41-50	.027	.787	Not significant
Age=51+	-.016	.874	Not significant
Position=Teacher I	.007	.945	Not significant
Position=Teacher II	-.004	.972	Not significant
Position=Teacher III	.052	.608	Not significant
Position=Master Teacher	-.074	.466	Not significant
Educational Attainment=College Graduate	-.004	.970	Not significant
Educational Attainment=Post Graduate/Doctorate	.004	.970	Not significant
Years of Service=1-5	-.007	.944	Not significant
Years of Service=6-10	-.036	.725	Not significant
Years of Service=11-15	.076	.454	Not significant
Years of Service=16+	-.022	.827	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Point-Biserial Correlation not significant at .05 level

These findings imply that there is no significant linear relationship between the respondents' attitudes of teachers and the profile characteristics examined in this study. In other words, factors such as sex, age, position, educational attainment, and years of service do not appear to have a substantial impact on teachers' attitudes as perceived by the respondents.

These results have important implications for understanding the factors influencing teachers' attitudes. While demographic characteristics and professional profiles are important aspects of teachers' identities, they may not necessarily influence their attitudes in the classroom as perceived by others. Instead, other factors such as pedagogical approaches, classroom management styles, and interpersonal interactions may play a more significant role in shaping teachers' attitudes and behaviors.

Educational stakeholders, including administrators, policymakers, and teacher training programs, should consider these findings when designing interventions or professional development initiatives aimed at improving teachers' attitudes. Rather than focusing solely on demographic or profile characteristics, efforts should be directed towards enhancing pedagogical skills, fostering positive classroom environments, and promoting effective communication and interpersonal relationships between teachers and learners.

Thus, while result reveals non-significant correlations between respondents' perceptions of teachers' attitudes and various profile characteristics, it underscores the complex nature of teacher attitudes and highlights the need for a multifaceted approach to understanding and promoting positive teaching practices within educational settings.

Accordingly, "Attitude can be positive or negative" is an often-used term. The positive attitudes of the teachers may result in an improvement in the performance of the learners. Negative attitudes from teachers, however, could affect learners' performance negatively. Teachers' attitudes have a direct or indirect, conscious, or unconscious, impact on learners' academic success. Extensive literature has been discussed on how the attitudes of teachers affect learners' performance. The motivation of learners to learn is greatly impacted by the attitudes of their teachers (Shittu & Oanite, 2018).

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' attitude of teachers and their behavioral competencies?

Table 20. Relationship between the Respondents' Attitude of Teachers and their Behavioral Competencies

Attitude of Teachers	Behavioral Competencies		Remarks
	r-value	p-value	
Supportive Teaching	-.045	.659	Not significant
Approachable Teaching	-.010	.920	Not significant
Considerate Teaching	.087	.390	Not significant
Positive Attitude	.017	.863	Not significant
Discriminatory Teaching	.036	.721	Not significant
Being Irritated	.183	.069	Not significant
Bias in Teaching	.140	.166	Not significant
Negative Attitude	.197*	.050	Significant
Total Measure	.122	.227	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Pearson Correlation not significant at .05 level

Table 20 presents the correlation results between the respondents' attitudes of teachers and their behavioral competencies, including supportive teaching, approachable teaching, considerate teaching, positive attitude, discriminatory teaching, being irritated, bias in

teaching, negative attitude, and the total measure.

The analysis indicates that most of the correlations between the respondents' attitudes of teachers and their behavioral competencies are not significant at the 0.05 level. For instance, attitudes towards supportive teaching, approachable teaching, considerate teaching, positive attitude, discriminatory teaching, bias in teaching, and the total measure do not show statistically significant correlations with the respondents' perceptions of teachers' attitudes.

However, the correlation between the respondents' attitudes towards being irritated and negative attitude shows a significant relationship with a p-value of 0.050. This suggests that there is a weak but significant positive correlation between the respondents' perceptions of teachers' attitudes towards being irritated and their overall negative attitude.

These findings imply that while there may not be significant correlations between specific behavioral competencies and attitudes of teachers as perceived by respondents in most cases, there is a noteworthy relationship between attitudes towards being irritated and overall negative attitude.

This result underscores the importance of considering teachers' emotional states, particularly their ability to manage frustration and maintain a positive demeanor in the classroom, as it may impact their overall attitude as perceived by others. Teachers' capacity to handle moments of irritation and maintain professionalism despite challenges is crucial for creating a positive learning environment and fostering positive relationships with learners and colleagues.

Educational stakeholders should take into account these findings when developing support mechanisms and professional development programs for teachers. Providing resources and strategies to help teachers effectively manage stress, handle conflicts, and maintain a positive attitude can contribute to improved classroom dynamics and student outcomes.

Thus, the result highlighted the nonsignificant correlations between most behavioral competencies and attitudes of teachers as perceived by respondents, it underscores the significance of addressing teachers' emotional well-being, particularly their ability to manage moments of irritation, in shaping overall attitudes. This insight can inform targeted interventions aimed at promoting positive teacher-student interactions and enhancing the overall educational experience.

Despite their severe demeanor, the pupils nevertheless value the teacher's provision of an equitable learning atmosphere free from discrimination. A student's sense of safety, confidence, and respect for their instructor all increase when they have a positive impression of them. Learners behave respectfully, feel at ease in the classroom, and pay greater attention in class when they feel valued (Wubbels, 2019). They contend that building strong relationships with learners fosters motivation, enthusiasm, and drive while satisfying learners' expectations of the class and the instructor, which influences their behavioral competencies.

Problem 6: Does the teachers' profile and attitude significantly predict the teachers' behavioral competencies?

Table 21. Regression Analysis of Predicting the Teachers' Behavioral Competencies by Profile and Attitudes

Predictors	Regression Coeff.,		t-value	p-value	Remarks
	B	Std. Error			
Sex=Female	-.006	.008	-.754	.453	Not significant
Age=25-30	-.006	.027	-.229	.820	Not significant
Age=31-35	.014	.024	.599	.550	Not significant
Age=36-40	.030	.022	1.351	.180	Not significant
Age=41-50	.012	.018	.682	.497	Not significant
Age=51+ (ref)	--	--	--	--	
Position=Teacher I	-.007	.019	-.356	.722	Not significant
Position=Teacher II	.009	.018	.509	.612	Not significant
Position=Teacher III	.005	.015	.337	.737	Not significant
Position=Master Teacher (ref)	--	--	--	--	
Educational Attainment=College Graduate	.002	.010	.199	.842	Not significant
Educational Attainment=Post Graduate/Doctorate (ref)	--	--	--	--	
Years of Service=1-5	-.007	.025	-.294	.770	Not significant
Years of Service=6-10	-.005	.023	-.226	.822	Not significant
Years of Service=11-15	-.011	.020	-.524	.602	Not significant
Years of Service=16+ (ref)	--	--	--	--	
Positive Attitude	-.028	.022	-1.259	.212	Not significant
Negative Attitude	.054	.023	2.380*	.020	Significant

Note: Analysis is based on Regression analysis Adjusted R2 = .063 *significant at .05 level

Table 21 presents the results of a regression analysis aimed at predicting teachers' behavioral competencies based on various profile characteristics and attitudes. The predictors include sex, age groups, position, educational attainment, years of service, positive attitude, and negative attitude.

The analysis reveals that most predictors are not significant in predicting teachers' behavioral competencies. Sex, age groups, position, educational attainment, years of service, and positive attitude do not have a statistically significant impact on behavioral competencies.

However, the negative attitude of teachers shows a significant positive regression coefficient ($B=0.054$, $p=0.020$), indicating that a more positive way in dealing negative attitude is associated with higher levels of behavioral competencies. This finding suggests that teachers who exhibit more right mechanisms against negative attitudes, as perceived by respondents, tend to demonstrate higher levels of behavioral competencies.

Further exploration is needed to understand the underlying dynamics and potential explanations for this unexpected relationship. It is possible that teachers who are more critical of their own performance or more aware of areas for improvement may actively work to enhance their behavioral competencies. Additionally, external factors not captured in this analysis may influence both teachers' attitudes and their behavioral competencies.

The adjusted R-squared value of 0.063 indicates that the predictors included in the model explain only a small portion of the variance in teachers' behavioral competencies.

Thus, the result provides some insights into the predictors of teachers' behavioral competencies, the significance of negative attitude warrants further investigation and consideration. Educational stakeholders should approach these findings with caution and explore additional factors that may influence teachers' attitudes and behaviors in the classroom. Further research is needed to better understand the complex interplay between attitudes, profile characteristics, and behavioral competencies among teachers.

Given its significant influence on student involvement, classroom management is a crucial subject in teacher education (Berger, Girardet, Vaudroz, & Crahay, 2018). The way the classroom is run has a big impact on how well learners do academically and how they behave. Managing learners' attitudes, personalities, vitalities, competencies, and passions is considered effective management (Suci, Tuerah, & Sumual, 2022). To motivate pupils to be cooperative, obedient, and participatory, teachers should concentrate on fostering a compassionate environment.

Problem 7: What action plan can be derived based on the results of the study?

Rationale

The action plan aims to enhance teachers' behavioral competencies by implementing a comprehensive set of strategies addressing various aspects of professional development and support. By offering targeted workshops, coaching, and mentoring programs, teachers will have the opportunity to improve their communication, classroom management, and facilitation skills, essential for creating a conducive learning environment.

Establishing peer support networks and communities of practice will further foster collaboration and knowledge-sharing among teachers, facilitating the exchange of best practices and strategies. Providing access to self-assessment tools and resources encourages teachers to engage in reflective practices, identifying areas for growth and setting personalized goals for improvement. Finally, fostering a culture of continuous improvement through recognition and celebration of teachers' achievements reinforces positive behaviors and contributes to a supportive and motivating work environment, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness and satisfaction of the teaching staff.

Conclusions

This study underscored a prevailing culture of dedication and excellence within the teaching profession, as evidenced by the high levels of positive attitude among teachers across supportive, approachable, and considerate teaching dimensions. Despite encountering challenges, such as discriminatory practices, frustrations while teaching, and biases in teaching practices, educators exhibit proactive efforts to address these issues, reflecting their commitment to promoting equality, managing classroom dynamics, and fostering inclusivity. Moreover, the consistently high level of proficiency demonstrated by teachers in communication, classroom management, and facilitation of engagement indicates their effectiveness in creating enriching learning environments and promoting student participation. Overall, these findings highlight the proactive approach and dedication of teachers towards student success and positive teaching practices.

This study also concluded that various demographic and attitudinal factors have limited predictive power in explaining teachers' attitudes and behavioral competencies as perceived by respondents. Factors such as sex, age, position, educational attainment, and years of service showed nonsignificant relationships with teachers' attitudes. Additionally, while most predictors in the regression analysis were not significant, a notable finding was the significant positive relationship between negative attitude and behavioral competencies.

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be proposed for different stakeholders within the educational ecosystem.

School Administrators. They may recognize and commend the prevailing culture of dedication and excellence among teachers, providing ongoing support and professional development opportunities to further enhance their positive attitudes and teaching practices.

Curriculum Planners. They may collaborate closely with teachers to develop curriculum materials and instructional strategies that actively promote inclusivity, diversity, and sensitivity to learners' needs, thereby addressing challenges related to discriminatory

practices and biases in teaching.

Teachers. They may continue their proactive efforts in managing classroom dynamics, fostering supportive learning environments, and engaging learners effectively, while also prioritizing self-care and seeking opportunities for personal and professional growth.

Learners. It is crucial for learners to foster a culture of mutual respect, understanding, and appreciation for diversity within the classroom, facilitated by teachers' positive attitudes and inclusive teaching practices.

Future Researchers. They may build upon this study by exploring additional factors that may influence teachers' attitudes and behavioral competencies, such as organizational culture, leadership styles, and external pressures.

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